

COMPARISON OF OUTCOME WITH THREE-PORT VERSUS CONVENTIONAL FOUR-PORT LAPAROSCOPIC CHOLECYSTECTOMY

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Abstract

Objective: To compare the outcomes of three-port laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) with the conventional four-port LC approach.

Methodology: This randomized controlled trial was conducted from January 2025 to April 2025 in the general surgery unit of Allama Iqbal Teaching Hospital, DG Khan. Patients aged 25–60 years of either male or female gender, presenting with acute cholecystitis, having ≤ 7-days symptom duration and planned for LC were included. The patients were randomly assigned to 3-port LC (Group A) and 4-port LC group (Group B). VAS pain score at 24 hours, total duration of oral analgesia and time to return to daily activities were primary study outcomes.

Results: Group A had a mean age of 41.1 (±8.6) years while Group B had a mean age of 39.8 (±9.3) years (p-value of 0.57). The Visual Analog Scale (VAS) score measured 24 hours post-operation was significantly lower in Group A, 1.7 ± 0.4 versus 2.9 ± 0.7 in group B (p-value <0.0001). Moreover, the duration of oral analgesia was notably reduced for Group A, averaging 3.4 ± 0.61 days versus 4.2 ± 0.9 days in group B (p-value <0.0001). Additionally, Group A experienced a quicker return to daily activities, 4.6 ± 0.7 days versus 5.5 ± 1.3 days in group B (p-value 0.001).

Conclusion: The three-port LC is safe and is linked to improved post-operative pain outcomes and a quicker return to daily life activities compared to four-port LC.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, surgeons have advanced their expertise in abdominal surgeries. While traditional open methods remain in use, many surgeons now favor minimally invasive techniques for most surgical procedures.¹ Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is a surgical technique that employs minimally invasive methods to remove a gallbladder affected by disease. The popularity of LC surged following the National Institute of Health Consensus Development Conference in September 1992, which established it as the standard treatment for gallstones, often

referred to as the "gold standard" in this area of care.^{2,3}

The laparoscopic approach to cholecystectomy is continuously advancing. Researchers and clinicians regularly evaluate various factors, such as the number and size of ports, to identify the optimal configuration.^{4,5} However, there are currently no established guidelines regarding the standard number of ports for routine cholecystectomies, and each configuration carries potential risks and complications. In traditional four-port cholecystectomy, the fourth trocar is positioned

laterally to grasp the gallbladder's fundus, allowing for better visualization of Calot's triangle.⁶

There has been discussion regarding the necessity of a fourth trocar in laparoscopic cholecystectomy, suggesting that this procedure can be completed safely without it. Recent research highlights the effectiveness of the three-port technique, which eliminates the fourth port and has shown promising results. Numerous studies indicate that minimizing either the size or quantity of ports correlates with reduced postoperative discomfort.^{7, 8} This study aims to compare the outcomes of 3-port LC with the conventional 4-port LC approach.

METHODOLOGY:

This randomized controlled trial was conducted from January 2025 to April 2025 in the general surgery unit of Allama Iqbal Teaching Hospital, DG Khan. Patients aged 25–60 years of either male or female gender, presenting with acute cholecystitis, having ≤ 7 -days symptom duration and planned for LC were included. Patients with a history of abdominal surgery in the last 3 months, uncontrolled coagulopathy (INR >1.5), carcinoma of the gall bladder, and chronic liver disease were excluded.

Demographic data including age, gender, obesity and duration of symptoms was noted. The patients were randomly assigned to 3-port LC (Group A) and 4-port LC (Group B) group using lottery methods. Sealed opaque envelopes containing slip marked with either A or B was picked by patients. The laparoscopic cholecystectomy was performed by experienced consultant surgeon with ≥ 5 -year post-fellowship experience. All the procedures were performed as per hospital protocol.

After surgery, all patients received antibiotics and pain relief medication according to the hospital's protocol. The level of pain was evaluated at the 24-hour mark using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS). Discharge decisions were made by the attending physician, and patients were scheduled for a follow-up visit on day 7 post-surgery. During this follow-up, their need for oral pain relief and the time taken to resume normal daily activities were assessed.

Data analysis was conducted with SPSS v25. We compared post-operative pain, duration of oral

analgesia, and time to resume normal activities across the groups using an independent sample t-test, taking p-value ≤ 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS:

Group A consisted of 30 participants who underwent a three-port surgical procedure, with an average age of 41.1 years (± 8.6). Conversely, Group B also had 30 participants but experienced a four-port procedure, with a mean age of 39.8 years (± 9.3), resulting in a p-value of 0.57 for age comparison. In terms of gender distribution, Group A included 6 males (20.0%) and 24 females (80.0%), whereas Group B comprised 5 males (16.7%) and 25 females (83.3%), yielding a p-value of 0.11, which indicates no significant difference. Regarding obesity prevalence, 8 individuals (26.7%) in Group A were reported as obese, compared to 10 individuals (33.3%) in Group B, resulting in a p-value of 0.57. Lastly, the symptom duration was comparable in both groups, with Group A averaging 2.3 days (± 1.5) and Group B averaging 2.1 days (± 1.6), leading to a p-value of 0.61. Overall, these results indicate that the two groups have similar key demographic and clinical characteristics (Table 1).

Table 2 presents a comparative analysis of the outcomes from the study involving two distinct groups. The results indicate that the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) score, assessed 24 hours after the operation, was significantly lower in Group A, averaging 1.7 ± 0.4 . In contrast, Group B recorded a higher average VAS score of 2.9 ± 0.7 (p-value less than 0.0001). Furthermore, the duration of oral analgesia was notably shorter for Group A, with an average of 3.4 ± 0.61 days, while Group B had a longer duration of 4.2 ± 0.9 days, also with a p-value of less than 0.0001. Additionally, Group A had a faster return to daily activities, averaging 4.6 ± 0.7 days, compared to Group B, whose participants took longer, averaging 5.5 ± 1.3 days, with a significant p-value of 0.001. These findings suggest that Group A required less pain medication and achieved a quicker recovery than Group B, highlighting the potential advantages of the intervention administered to Group A.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics.

	Group A (3 Port) (N=30)	Group B (4 Port) (N=30)	P-value
Age (Y)	41.1±8.6	39.8±9.3	0.57
Gender (%)			
Male	06 (20.0%)	05 (16.7%)	0.11
Female	24 (80.0%)	25 (83.3%)	
Obesity (%)			
Yes	08 (26.7%)	10 (33.3%)	0.57
No	22 (73.3%)	20 (66.7%)	
Durations of Symptoms (days)	2.3±1.5	2.1±1.6	0.61

Table 2. Comparison of Study Outcomes.

	Group A (3 Port) (N=30)	Group B (4 Port) (N=30)	P-value
24-hour post-operative VAS	1.7±0.4	2.9±0.7	<0.0001
Duration of oral analgesia (days)	3.4±0.61	4.2±0.9	<0.0001
Time to return to daily activities (days)	4.6±0.7	5.5±1.3	0.001

DISCUSSION:

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is globally recognized as the definitive treatment for gallstone-related conditions. Recent advancements are emerging in this field, focusing on improving procedural expertise. The primary objective of minimally invasive surgery is to minimize postoperative discomfort, enhance aesthetic outcomes, and facilitate quicker recovery times.⁵ A significant enhancement in patient outcomes has been observed with the reduction in the number and size of trocars used.^{9, 10} The strategy of decreasing the number of ports utilized has been a topic of ongoing discussion among surgeons worldwide.¹¹ This study aims to evaluate and compare the common immediate and short-term complications experienced by patients undergoing either three-port or four-port laparoscopic procedures.

Mohamed et al. enrolled 94 patients with symptomatic gallstone disease, randomly assigning them to either the three-port LC group (45 patients) or the four-port LC group (49 patients). The results showed that the Numeric Pain Rating Scale scores were significantly lower in the three-port group (2.03±0.91 vs. 2.87±1.14), as were the average number of diclofenac ampoules used (3.25±0.9 vs. 4.12±0.54), the duration for oral analgesia (3.5±0.55 vs. 4.6±0.92 days), and the time required to return to normal activities (4.9±0.92 vs. 5.7±1.75 days). The

rates of intraoperative and postoperative complications were similar between the two groups.¹² In a comparable study, Chohan S et al. enrolled 100 patients suffering from symptomatic gallstone disease, who were randomly assigned to Group A (conventional 4-port LC) and Group B (3-port LC). The three-port LC group exhibited a lower mean VAS score for post-operative pain (2.44±0.61 compared to 4.52±1.07; p-value<0.0001) than the four-port LC group. Nevertheless, there was no significant difference regarding the frequency of CBD injury (2.0% vs. 0.0%; p-value=0.315) or wound infection rates (6.0% vs. 8.0%; p-value=0.695).¹³

Shoukat et al., in their study comparing 3-port and 4-port LC, reported that the outcomes of 3-port LC are comparable to 4-port LC in terms of post-op pain, occurrence of infections, and conversion to open LC. Moreover, the authors reported shorter hospital stays in the 3 port LC group.¹⁴

Kumar and colleagues performed a comprehensive analysis to compare the effectiveness of 3-port LC with the traditional 4-port LC. Findings indicated that the three-port method resulted in significantly reduced port-site pain, produced comparable clinical outcomes, led to fewer visible surgical scars, and did not increase the risk of bile duct injury when compared to the four-port approach.¹⁵

A comprehensive analysis comparing three-port and four-port LC, conducted by Hajibandeh et al., demonstrated that the three-port approach is equally effective as the four-port method regarding procedural outcomes and complications. Furthermore, it appears to result in less postoperative discomfort, reduced hospital stay duration, and quicker recovery to normal activities.⁸ Our findings align with the results obtained in this study.

Conclusion:

The three-port LC is safe and is linked to improved post-operative pain outcomes and a quicker return to daily life activities compared to four-port LC.

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